

DATA NOTEBOOKS, boxes 262-272

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No.

box
262

000	—		Visual Obs'ns (Peru)	8/1894 - 7/1896	S. I. Bailey
001	1		Variable stars in W Cen	11/1898 - 12/1898	" "
002	2		" " W Cen, M5	2/1899 - 8/1901	" "
003	3		" " M3	6/1900 - 9/1901	" "
004	4		" " M3, M5	12/1901 - 9/1912	" "
005	—		" " NGC 7078, 6656, M22	7/1907 - 10/1920	" + Gould
006	—		Msc. Var. + " " NGC 7078, 6656, M3, M5	1/1902; 4/1910 - 12/1915	" "
007	—		Var. Stars in many clusters	5/1922 - 2/1923	" "
008	G1		Star counts, Neb. on Map of Sky, LMC, Glob.	3/1906 - 1/1907	" "
009	G2		Nebulae	1/1907 - 9/1908	" "
010	G3		Nebulae	9/1908 - 10/1911	" "
011	G4	V. I	Positions of Nebulae	4/1908 - 7/1908	?
012	G5	V. III	" " "	9/1908 - 10/1908	?
013	G6	V. IV	" " "	10/1908 - 12/1908	?
014	G7	V. V	" " "	12/1908 - 3/1909	?
015	G8	V. VI	" " "	3/1909 - 4/1909	?
016	G9	V. VII	" " "	4/1909 - 8/1909	?
017	G10	V. VIII	" " "	6/1909 - 9/1909	?
018	G11	V. IX	" " "	9/1909 - 10/1909	?
019	G12	V. X	" " "	11/1909 - 8/1910	?
020	G13	V. XI	" " "	8/1910 - 9/1910	?
021	G14	1	" " " marked by Dr. Shalley	? - 7/1923	?
022	G15	2	" " " " " "	7/1923 - 8/1923	Leon Campbell, Jr.
023	G16	1	" " " disc. by D. Menzel	7/1922 - 8/1922	D. Menzel
024	G17	2	" " " " " "	8/1922	" "
025	G18	3	" " " " " "	8/1922	" "
026	G19	4	" " " " " "	8/1922	" "
027	G20	1	" " " Coma - Virgo	2/1927 - 3/1927	A. Ames
028	G21	2	" " " " " "	1927?	" "
029	G22	3	" " " " " "	1927?	" "
030	G23	4	" " " " " "	?	" "
031	G24	5	" " " " " "	?	" "
032	G25	6	Diam. Conc. Form "	"	" "
033	G26	7	Positions, Magn, dia	"	" "
034	G27	8	" " " " " "	"	" "
035	G28	9	" " S. Gal. Pole	"	" "
036	G29	10	" " " C.-V. ^{ext.} -30° to -60°	"	" "
037	G30	11	Ident + Mag. NGC Objects	"	" "
038	G31	12	" " Coma - Vir set.	"	" "

box
263

box
268

117	G113	Magnitudes of Nebulae		C.D. Ba
118	G114	Magnitudes, Diameters of Nebulae		R.L. Paraboloschi
119	G115	Magnitudes of Nebulae		F.W. Wright
120	G116	Mags. on Overlapping Plates		"
121	G117 M1	15 th Mag. Survey		J. Mohr
122	G118 M2	" " "		"
123	G119	" " "	1935	N.J. Oliver
124	G125	Classification + Diameter		C.K. Seyfert
125	G126	" "		"
126	G127 1	Positions		"
127	G128	Magnitudes		"
128	G129	Magnitudes		"
129	G130	MC Records of Nebulae; Summary		
130	G131	MC Magnitude of Nebulae		M.E.M
131	G132	MC Classification + Diameters		
132	G133	MC Nebula Count		
133	G134	MC North Polar Cap: Positions		
134	G135	MC Plate Centers		
135	G136	MC North Polar Cap: Magnitudes		P.B.J
136	G137	" " " "		
137	G138 MCVII	MC Magnitudes		
138	G139 MCVIII	" "		
139	G140 MCIX	" "		
140	G141 MCX	" "		
141	G142 MCXI	" "		
142	G143 MCXII	" "		
143	G144 MCXIII	" "		
144	G145 MCXIV	" "		
145	G146 MCXV	" "		
146	1	Variables in SMC, LMC	1935-39	RK Marshall FWW, VMcK RACraig VMcK, N. A.F. Swain VMcK N
147	2	" " "		
148	3	" "		
149	4	" Vela-Carina		FWW
150	5	" SMC	1945	A.S. Carlston
151	6a	" "		FWW, VMcK
152	6b	" LMC, SMC	1941, 51	S&B, FWW A. Neary M.D. Ashworth FWW, VMcK RK Marshall E.M. Coote VMcK Nail
153	8	" " "		
154	9	" SMC		
155	10	" "		

Box
269

Box
269

Box
290

Books in
good
condition;
numbers
on
front
covers

156 11
 157 12
 158 13
 159 14
 160 15
 161 16
 162 18
 163 19
 164 28
 165 30
 166 31
 167 32
 168 33
 169 34
 170 35
 171 FW1
 172 FW2
 173 FW3
 174 FW4
 175 FW5
 176 FW Var.1
 177 FW Var.2
 178 FW Var.3
 179 FW Blk III
 180 FW
 181 11
 182 12
 183 13
 184 17
 185
 186
 187 2
 188
 189 No.1
 190 No.2
 191 No.3
 192 43
 193
 194

Variables in SMC, 30 Dor
 " " 47 Tuc
 " LMC, SMC.
 " " "
 " SMC, 47 Tuc, NGC 362
 " SMC, LMC
 " SMC
 MWF 182, MWF 188, SMC, LMC
 M55, LMC variables
 Variables in LMC
 " "
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 " LMC, SMC
 Variables in LMC (HA 90 #1)
 " LMC
 " " SMC
 " " "
 Red variables "
 Var's in NGC 1846, 2315
 Var's in ω Cen, NGC 4833, NGC 7099
 Var's in NGC 3201
 " " "
 Milky Way Bureau, Red Magns
 Leo I - periods; Vela
 Variables in ω Cen
 " " "
 " " " ; misc var's
 K Crucis
 Hercules Cluster
 Messier 5
 ω Centauri; Eros 2.
 Measurements of Clusters
 Discussion of Measures of Clusters
 Measures of Clusters
 Measures Cl. in Per; Obs + Magn.
 Work on Mag. Cls. 1924-25
 Var's in Aql, Sct - mostly NA plates

M. R. Hunt
 VMcK.
 yMcK.
 M. S. Matthews
 VMcKN
 FWW et al.
 VMcKNail
 ?
 1932 M. B. Leavens
 M. B. Shapley
 VMcKN
 1934 J. Mohr + VMcK
 1954-55 VMcKNail
 B. Lindway
 VMcKN
 1952 M. Ryder
 1950 M. L. Miller
 1953-54 J. Swartzman
 W. Tiffet
 H. S. Led with
 S. F. Missals
 VMcK, et al.
 Various
 Various
 VMcKNail
 FWW?
 FWW et al
 FWW et al.
 FWW et al.
 FWW
 FWW
 E. F. Heland
 "
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 ?
 ?
 I. E. Woods
 E. L. ?
 1903 F. E. Brasch
 1924-25 H. H. Wilson
 S. E. M. Mindemus
 E. F. Sanborn
 1931-37

Box 271

195 ~~42~~
 196 42
 197
 198 53
 199 ~~42~~
 200
 201
 202 15
 203
 204 IIa
 205
 206 S.G. III
 207 S.G. IV
 208 S.G. V
 209 S.F. V

Shorthand notes
 Cluster in Perseus, Pos + mag.
 Variables in LMC
 Misc. Variables
 Variables in Car. + Vel
 Measurements at Maria Mitchell
 Work on spectra
 Misc. Var Star Work
 Tests on 60-in Telescope
 LMC Variables - mags.
 Sequences in SMC
 SA 194-195; SA 197-199
 SA 196
 SA 188-194
 SA 177-182

1921-26 H. Shapley
 1903 S.E. Breslin
 ~1931? S.F. Russell
 F.W. Wright
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 1921 H. Shapley
 1921-46 A. Walker
 1924-26
 1931 Natalie Ross
 A. Ames
 S. Gaposchki
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Box 272

210
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 212
 213
 214
 215
 216
 217
 218
 219
 220
 221
 222 A
 223 B
 224 C
 225 D
 226 E
 227 F
 228 G
 229 H
 230 I
 231 J
 232 K
 233 L
 234

Star counts of the LMC
 Bright Variable Star Survey, Field 8
 Measures of Peruvian Pole Star Plates
 VSF Variables SA 16, MWF 208, Anticenter 601 +17.6, 122, 190
 VSF " MSF 299, 305, 679 + 298
 Positions of Variables around LMC
 Sequences in LMC
 Nebulous Objects in MCs
 AM Plate Milky Way Atlas
 Clusters in MCs
 "Milky Way Borders" (publ. in HA 106 #3)
 Positions in ω Cen
 O-stars; P-Cygni stars
 Spectra - η Car and others
 Spectra
 Spectral Classification - Bright Stars
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1901 ?
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 L.R. Ford lays
 A.B. Hearn
 T.K.
 M.W.
 1953 M.S. Matthei
 V. McK. Neil
 ?
 H. Shapley
 V. McK. Neil
 H. Shapley
 J. Sweeney et al.
 A. Walker
 D. Hoffleit
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